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Identifying high-impact consumers' behavioural changes for flexibility and demand reduction in a net-zero energy system

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Abstract

Achieving decarbonization across energy sectors requires demand-side transformation such as behavioural changes and end-use efficiency improvements to complement supply-side technological shifts. However, changing consumption patterns is challenging, and implementing efficiency measures requires time and investment, highlighting the need to prioritize strategies. We address this prioritization using a high-resolution model of the European energy system under net-zero emissions, assessing the system-wide impacts of reducing or shifting energy service demand across power, heating, transport, aviation, shipping, industry, and agriculture. Four stylised mechanisms (constant reduction, peak shaving, temporal shifting, and curtailment) that can be mapped to real-world phenomena are assessed for their impacts on system costs, electricity and heating prices, CO₂ price, and capacity needs. Results indicate that demand flexibility and curtailment yield the greatest benefits: shifting demand by 2 hours to align with solar output reduces system costs by 0.4%, while curtailing 3.7% of electricity demand during peak price periods cuts costs by 0.9%.

Introduction

Reductions in average or peak demand across different sectors can result from technological shifts (electric vehicles or heat pumps with flexible operation substituting fossil-based transport or heating provision), more efficient use of final energy (using smaller vehicles, enhanced insulation through buildings retrofitting) or through behavioural changes (less commuting due to home office or setting a lower target for indoor thermostats). Technological changes maintain energy service demand while altering the demand for different energy carriers, mostly through electrification. In contrast, the second and third types of alterations reduce the energy service demand. While most modern energy system models represent technological shifts^[1],

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alterations in energy service demand are typically absent or assumed exogenously due to the difficulties of assigning a cost to them^{2,6}. In this paper, we implement four stylised mechanisms to represent potential alterations in energy service demand (constant demand reduction, peak shaving, temporal shifting, and demand curtailment) into a sector-coupled model that includes an accurate representation of technological shifts.

We have recently witnessed alterations in energy service demands that represent concrete examples of our stylised mechanisms at scale. The COVID-19 pandemic triggered long-lasting changes in mobility patterns through remote work, public information campaigns during Europe’s gas crisis in 2022 led to a lower heating demand in winter⁷, and emergency alerts during a recent Californian heatwave cut demand by 4% within minutes⁸. As consumers’ motivation for reducing demand remains low globally,⁹ achieving long-term demand alterations requires targeted policies and investment, for example, enabling rail to compete with air travel for mid-distance trips¹⁰.

An extensive literature exists where potential reductions in service demand are estimated for different sectors, including buildings¹¹, transport¹², and other sectors for sufficiency-oriented scenarios in Europe¹³. These pre-computed demand reductions have been integrated into various modeling frameworks and found to be an effective strategy to attain climate change mitigation while easing the urgency for large-scale deployment of NETs technologies such as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)⁶. Grubler et al.² showed that a global 1.5°C pathway without NETs is achievable by reducing final energy demand by 40%. Costa et al.³ described a 2°C target without BECCS through ambitious behavioural and technological changes. Wiese et al.⁴ found a 40% service demand reduction feasible in Europe, lowering dependence on carbon sequestration, energy imports, and nuclear power. Demand reductions also mitigate land-use change^{3,6}, decrease material requirements, and ease the economic and social burden of the transition¹⁴.

Previous studies assume exogenous energy service demand reductions, lacking temporal resolution and detailed sector coupling to investigate capacity requirements and cross-sector impacts. This type of demand alteration is represented in our first stylised mechanism: constant demand reductions across sectors.

Using a high-resolution energy system model, Zeyen et al.¹⁵ co-optimized heating supply technologies and building renovations, finding that heating demand could be reduced by up to 51%, primarily driven by peak rather than annual demand reductions. Our second stylised mechanism reflects this peak-average dynamic by shaving peak demand across sectors. Zhu et al.¹⁶ demonstrated how building thermal inertia can shift heating loads and reduce storage needs, while Riepin et al.¹⁷ showed cost savings from spatial and temporal load shifting in data centres. Our third stylised mechanism enables temporal demand shifting, but instead of prescribing shift characteristics based on real-world phenomena, the model endogenously determines the timing and extent of demand shifting, allowing insights to emerge from system optimization. Finally, Brown et al.¹⁸ showed that incorporating modest demand elasticity improves market dynamics and stabilizes prices. Our fourth stylised mechanism represents a one-step demand flexibility curve, allowing demand curtailment

when prices exceed a defined threshold.

In this study, we investigate the impact of varying energy service demand using a 2-hourly resolved model that captures technological shifts reducing final demand, as well as flexibility from storage and transmission. In contrast with previous literature, we do not predefine demand reductions based on assumed sufficiency or behavioural changes. Instead, we implement four stylised mechanisms that can be assimilated to real-world phenomena: the first two apply exogenous constant and peak demand reductions in different sectors, while the third and fourth allow the system to endogenously determine temporal shifting and curtailment of demand. We apply these to a net-zero European energy system to assess their effects on total system cost, electricity and heating price levels and variability, CO₂ price as a proxy for policy needs, required capacities, and cross-sectoral impacts.

Results and discussion

Heating is a priority for constant reduction and peak shaving

The base scenario (Fig. 1) for a net-zero emissions system has an annual cost of 936 bn€/a and requires a carbon price of 490 €/tCO₂ (see Methods). The system cost comprises primarily wind and solar, heat pumps and power-to-X technologies (Supplementary Fig. S4). All service demand alterations in different sectors reduce system cost, albeit depending on the sector and type of demand alteration, the cost reduction, impact on CO₂ price, and system configuration vary.

For constant demand reduction, system cost decreases linearly with the reduction level for all sectors (Fig. 2). Heating and industry yield the largest absolute cost savings when demand is uniformly reduced (Fig. 2a), which is expected as these are the sectors with highest energy demands (Fig. 1a). Reducing their demand cuts the need for costly technologies like heat pumps, electrolysers and Fischer-Tropsch units, and indirectly lowers wind and solar capacities. Relative to annual demand, constant reductions in aviation and shipping demand show the highest benefits (Supplementary Fig. S5).

CO₂ price reductions are highest for aviation, industry, and shipping, which are sectors with exogenous demands for oil, gas, and methanol (Fig. 1b). In our model, carbonaceous fuels can have fossil origin or be synthetically produced, but their offset is limited by the assumed CO₂ underground sequestration potential of 200 MtCO₂/year. Interestingly, large demand reduction in hard-to-abate sectors only reduces the CO₂ price by around 5% while larger variations were obtained when increasing the CO₂ sequestration potential¹⁹.

Lower demand means lower generation capacities are installed and less CO₂ needs to be captured (Fig. 2b-c). Demand reduction in heating, industry and electricity causes the largest decrease in installed capacities of wind and solar. Demand reductions unlock resources that are used to ease the supply of heating demand peaks. For instance, demand reductions in aviation and shipping, enable slightly higher CO₂ emissions in other sectors, which are used primarily by gas boilers. Demand reductions in industry decrease the

Fig. 1: **Sector demands.** Summary of (a) annual demand per sector, (b) temporal pattern of sectorial demands (rolling daily mean), (c) spatial distribution of demand, and (d) weekly average profile of demand for different sectors included in the model. The sectors are referred to as electricity (residential and commercial), heating (residential and commercial), land transport, industry, shipping, aviation, and agriculture. Only electricity, heating, and land transport have a temporal component.

exogenous demand for biomass which is then used in biomass-fired boilers and CHP units. For heating, shipping and aviation, demand reduction decreases the need for Direct Air Capture (DAC) significantly (see Supplementary Fig. S8 and further discussion later).

In the second set of scenarios, peak shaving is applied to sectors with hourly demand profiles. Cost savings grow exponentially with the share of peak shaving across all sectors, though at varying rates (Fig. 2d). Heating delivers the largest cost savings from peak shaving since supplying heat demand peaks is challenging, as anticipated from previous results. Savings are accomplished by reducing capacity of resistive heaters and gas boilers. Shaving heat peaks by 40% curbs total demand by 5% (inset Fig. 2d) and reduces system cost by 4.5%, while reducing heating demand by 5% uniformly only reduces the system cost by 2.5% (see Fig. 2a). Therefore, peak shaving is a more effective strategy for heating compared to the first mechanism (Supplementary Fig. S6).

Electricity and land transport exhibit similar cost reductions for peak shaving, resulting from a combination of two factors. Land transport shows nearly double annual demand reduction per shaved peak unit compared

Fig. 2: **System-wide impacts of four demand-alteration mechanisms.** Variation of: (a,d,g,i) Total system costs, (b,e,h,k) CO₂ price, and (c,f,i,l) installed capacity of selected system components for different demand alteration scenarios relative to the base scenario. All figures show results for scenarios that reduce demand in one sector (e.g. 40% demand reduction for aviation in a,b,c), while demand in other sectors remains the same. For figures (c,f,i,l) only the scenarios with highest demand alteration in each sector are shown. Inset in figure (d) shows the share of annual demand reduction as a function of the peak shaving level. The inset in figure (g) shows share of annual demand shifted to free storage size (size is measured as the ratio of energy capacity to annual demand of the sector). The inset in figure (j) shows share of annual demand curtailed for different load shedding prices (€/MWh). Scenarios marked with a green star are nearly equivalent in terms of alteration in demand accounting for 5% of annual demand in all of them. See Supplementary Fig. S8 for relative changes in installed capacities in different scenarios.

to electricity, but it is compensated by the fact that land transport attains roughly half of the savings per unit of demand reduced (Figs. 2d and 2a). In contrast to heating, savings from peak shavings in these two sectors is only slightly higher than constant reduction (Supplementary Fig. S6).

Peak shaving has an overall minor impact on CO₂ price. It decreases up to 2% for heating, a greater effect than equivalent constant reduction due to a lower use of high-emission backup technologies like gas boilers.

Aligning demand with solar generation is the most effective strategy

In the third set of scenarios, we model a free, lossless storage to represent demand shifting via behavioural changes, with the energy capacity of the free storage being fixed in each scenario (Fig. 2g). The assumed size for the free storage is limited, enabling only intraday demand shifting rather than seasonal shifts (Supplementary Fig. S13). Temporal shifting of electricity demand shows a higher impact on system costs because alternative short-term balancing via batteries is more expensive than for heating via thermal energy storage in water tanks.

For electricity, a free storage with energy capacity equal to 0.02% of annual demand (1.8 hours of average demand) enables shifting 5% of total annual demand, and reduces system cost by 0.4% (marked with green star in Fig. 2g). In our analogy, this would require convincing electricity consumers in residential and commercial sectors to relocate around 2 hours of demand to different times of the day. To put this number into perspective, the cost savings that this could attain are roughly half of those obtained by 40% electricity peak shaving (1% cost reduction) or constant demand reduction of 5% (0.8% cost reduction).

The system uses the free storage mimicking behavioural changes to make demand profiles follow solar generation (Fig. 3). For solar-dominated grids, such as Spain, this pattern is robust. For wind-dominated regions and seasons, such as Denmark in winter, the more random wind generation patterns make the shifted demand profiles less stable across different days.

Demand shifting modifies the optimal capacities, increasing static solar PV, while reducing horizontal single-axis tracking PV and battery storage. Batteries help daily balancing and tracking PV increases morning and evening generation, attributes which lose value when demand is shifted to noon. Since the free storage is assumed to be at the low-voltage level, rooftop PV capacity increases more than utility PV to prevent the losses occurring when transporting utility solar generation via distribution grids.²⁰

A free storage in the heating sector could mimic the usage of thermal inertia in buildings, e.g. by pre-heating the building during the day and reducing heating demand at night while maintaining indoor comfort levels, as discussed in a previous study¹⁶. This reduces the need for optimal thermal energy storage capacity (Supplementary Fig. S9). However, the cost reductions captured by demand-shifting in the heating sectors are limited by (i) the existence of cheap thermal energy storage in the form of water tanks, and (ii) limited capacity assumed for the free storage preventing seasonal balancing or peak demand supply (Supplementary Fig. S14), which are the main challenges in this sector.

Fig. 3: **Electricity demand profile shift.** Weekly average electricity demand profile (dark blue) for (a) Spain in summer, (b) Spain in winter, (c) Denmark in winter, and (d) Denmark in summer. The shifted demand (light blue) shows how the profile changes when a free storage with energy capacity equal to 0.1% of total electricity demand is available. The free storage represents consumers behavioural changes that shift their demand in time. The shifted demand is calculated by adding the net power being discharged from the free storage (negative when charging happens) to the demand.

A free storage in the land transport sector has a negligible impact on the system cost since this sector already includes free EV batteries. The energy capacity of the lumped EV batteries is equivalent to 1.3% of the annual land transport demand, with half of idle EVs supporting smart charging and V2G at each time step (see [Methods](#)).

Although the benefits of demand time shifting are smaller than those of the previous two mechanisms for both electricity and heating (Supplementary Fig. [S6](#)), it requires less effort, as consumers only need to reschedule their demand rather than reduce it.

Curtailling demand during critical hours is a priority

The fourth set of scenarios includes a stylised representation of demand elasticity by enabling demand curtailment in different sectors when energy prices rise above a certain threshold. The threshold is varied across scenarios. Similar cost reductions to those for the other mechanisms could be attained. For example, for the electricity sector, a threshold of 250 €/MWh, curtails 3.7% of annual demand and reduces total system cost by 0.9% (marked with a green star in Fig. [2j](#)). This is comparable to the cost reduction achieved by other green star scenarios: a 5% constant demand reduction (0.8% cost reduction), 40% electricity peak

shaving (1% cost reduction) and a free storage capable of shifting 5% of annual demand (0.4% cost reduction).

Cost reductions from load shedding are similar in electricity and land transport, since the latter is fully electrified. They are also similar for the heating. While one would expect that curtailing electricity is more effective than heat (since heat pumps can convert 1 kWh of electricity into 3 kWh or heat), demand curtailment occurs in periods of high heating demand in which resistive heaters are extensively used, making the curtailment of one unit of electricity or heat demand roughly equivalent. Overall, demand curtailment is the most effective strategy for lowering system costs and carbon prices across all three sectors (Supplementary Fig. S6), rivalled only by peak shaving for the heating sector in reducing costs.

For all sectors, allowing demand curtailment reduces dependence on gas turbines, gas-fired CHP units, and consequently DAC to compensate for CO₂ emissions of these plants (Fig. 2 and Supplementary Fig. S8). Heat pumps are sized to cover base heating demand, and their capacity is less affected. When demand is curtailed in electricity and land transport, the system installs more resistive heaters that use newly available electricity to meet heat demand.

Fig. 4: **Temporal and spatial pattern of load shedding** (a) Curtailed electricity demand time series for different load shedding prices. (b) Curtailed electricity demand for different countries as load shedding price increases. (c) Share of curtailed electricity from annual electricity demand for European countries when load shedding price is equal to 200 €/MWh.

Demand curtailment mainly occurs in winter (Fig. 4a), in periods when renewable generation is low and demand is high. While exact timing varies with the assumed load shedding price, winter consistently

dominates. Load shedding is known to be triggered by the overlapping of wind energy droughts, seasonally low solar generation, and high demand driven by low temperatures²¹. Germany, Poland, and the Netherlands see the highest absolute demand curtailment (Fig. 4b), with northern Europe leading in relative terms (Fig. 4c). This is in agreement with previous results showing Germany and other interior countries becoming net energy importers in net-zero scenarios²².

Prices become more stable by peak shaving and curtailment

Demand-weighted average electricity prices, based on the Lagrange multiplier of the energy balance constraint, decrease in all countries under various scenarios (Fig. 5). We compare here scenarios altering 5% of annual demand (shown for electricity as green star in Fig. 2 and for heating in Supplementary Fig. S17).

A constant demand reduction of 5% in either electricity or heating has negligible impacts on average electricity price and variation (Figs. 5a-b), because although lower capacities are installed, the difficulty of meeting demand, which sets the price, remains unchanged. In contrast, 40% peak shaving reduces prices by an average of 1.2% (electricity) and 5% (heating), with variability dropping by 6% (electricity) and 12% (heating). Heating peaks thus play a bigger role in price formation than electricity peaks.

A free storage has negligible impacts on price average for the electricity and heating sector. Impact on price variability is not uniform, with some countries experiencing a reduction of 10% (Figs. 5e-f). Demand curtailment results in strongest price reduction: 3% for electricity and 4% for heating, as well as the largest reduction in price variability: 28% for electricity and 31% for heating (Figs. 5g-h and Supplementary Fig. S18). This is because demand curtailment allows removing rarely-used backup capacities. Price impacts vary by country. Nations more constrained in meeting demand, like Germany or the Netherlands, gain more from demand temporal shifting and shedding. Meanwhile, energy exporters like Spain and Italy experience minimal benefits from these mechanisms.

Reducing reliance on carbon capture

Our model includes a detailed accounting of carbon management where CO₂ can be captured from point sources (biogas upgrading, biomass and gas used in CHP units and industry, process emissions) and DAC, and then be used to produce synthetic carbonaceous fuels (methane, methanol or oil) or sequestered underground (see [Methods](#), Supplementary Fig. S21). Most demand reduction scenarios reduce DAC but point-source capture and sequestration are less impacted.

Reductions in energy services demand have been suggested as a strategy to attain climate change mitigation with diminished critical reliance on negative emission technologies². In our results, constant demand reductions of 30% in aviation or 40% in heating or shipping eliminate the need for DAC entirely; however, this finding is limited to the sectoral emissions represented in our model, which, for instance, excludes non-energy agricultural emissions from fertilizers, livestock, etc. Similarly, 50% heating peak shaving or

Fig. 5: **Impacts of four demand alteration mechanisms on electricity price.** Country-wise changes in (a,c,e,g) annual average of demand-weighted shadow price of electricity, and (b,d,f,h) the standard deviation of demand-weighted shadow price of electricity, for (a,b) 5% total demand reduction, (c,d) 40% peak shaving, (e,f) free storage size equal to 0.02% of total electricity demand, and (g,h) load shedding with price of 250 €/MWh. The selected scenarios are almost equivalent in terms of total demand change. In some countries, prices rise (green in maps), as country-wise system costs are uneven due to local factors like PV expansion (Supplementary Figs. [S19](#)-[S20](#)).

curtailing 8% of electricity demand (with load shedding price of 200€/MWh) cuts DAC capacity by about 80% (Supplementary Figs. S8-S22).

The assumed CO₂ sequestration potential (200 MtCO₂/a) is only slightly higher than the exogenously fixed industrial process emissions in the model (127 MtCO₂/a). This limits offsetting emissions and effectively means that almost all exogenous demands for carbonaceous fuels (oil in aviation and industry, methanol in shipping) must be synthetically produced. When service demand reduction in one of the sectors makes attaining carbon neutrality easier, the additional freedom is used to consume more fossil fuels. For instance, a constant reduction in heating demand (lower emissions associated with methane) or industry demand (lower process emissions and those associated with oil) increases the use of fossil oil for aviation. Conversely, a constant reduction in aviation (lower emissions associated with oil) increases the use of methane for heating (Supplementary Fig. S11). Note that while net emissions are constrained to zero across all demand alteration mechanisms, the system's emission intensity (per unit of final energy demand) increases in some scenarios (Supplementary Fig. S21).

Discussion and conclusions

We have used four stylised mechanisms (constant demand reduction, peak shaving, demand shifting in time, and demand curtailment) to represent alteration in energy service demand in a net-zero European energy system and showed that all of them reduce system cost.

Constant demand reduction is more effective for the heating sector, underscoring the need for building retrofiting¹⁵. Taking into account sector demand size, aviation and shipping deliver the highest reductions in system costs and carbon prices under this mechanism (Supplementary Fig. S5). Decreasing demand uniformly in various sectors does not impact the average price of electricity or heat, but reduces the reliance on Direct Air Capture (DAC), particularly for constant reduction in the aviation, shipping and heating sectors, derisking the transition.

Demand shifting in time is particularly beneficial for residential and commercial electricity demand. Here, allowing the system to shift losslessly 2 hours of demand within every day reduces the system cost by 0.4% (which is already half of the cost reduction attained with a constant 5% electricity demand reduction). The system uses this flexibility to make demand overlap with solar generation. For solar-dominated grids, such as Spain across the year or Denmark in summer (Fig. 3), this pattern is robust and suggests the need for public intervention to motivate these demand shifts, including communication campaigns and setting grid tariffs to incentivise consumption when it is sunny. Notice that this is the opposite of historical grid tariffs that incentivised consumption during the nighttime. This should no longer be the case. We do not aim any more for a constant demand profile to reduce the required capacity, but for a bell-shaped demand profile to benefit from the cheapest electricity source available²³.

Demand curtailment was also found to be effective in reducing the system cost. For instance, for the

electricity sector, a threshold of 250 €/MWh, curtails 3.7% of annual demand and reduces total system cost by 0.9%. Although our stylised model might be very optimistic and 250 €/MWh might not be high enough to trigger instantaneous reductions in residential and commercial demands, industry consumers have higher demand elasticity (not modeled in our paper). Our results underscore the need for including demand flexibility in cost-optimisation energy system models, as highlighted by Brown and co-authors¹⁸, and for quantifying the elasticity of future industry demand (volumes and cost of energy deferral).

Methods

Modeling framework

We use the open sector-coupled model PyPSA-Eur²⁴ to analyse how changes in energy service demand influence the capacity and cost structure of a net-zero European energy system. The model represents Europe using 37 nodes, which are synchronous zones. Simulations are conducted for a full year with a 2-hourly time resolution, assuming perfect foresight throughout the year, utilizing 2013 weather data and cost assumptions from the technology data v0.9.0²⁵ corresponding to 2030.

We use a greenfield approach, assuming the entire energy system is built from scratch, except for the existing transmission network of AC and DC lines and hydropower plants, which are considered exogenously to be at today’s capacities. The overnight approach allows for fast optimization and parallel running of many alternative scenarios, enabling us to focus on the main impacts of different service demand reduction strategies across sectors. Transmission network is based on ENTSOE²⁶ and can be expanded by 20% compared to today’s volume. The distribution grid is modeled in each node as a single connection from the high-voltage (HV) to the low-voltage (LV) electricity bus with a 97% efficiency²⁰.

We set a net-zero CO₂ emissions target. The CO₂ price is obtained as the shadow price or Lagrange multiplier of this constraint and it is an indicator of the system’s difficulty in achieving net-zero emissions and the carbon price required to make certain technologies such as carbon capture economic. A maximum of 200 MtCO₂/y is allowed to be sequestered underground in every scenario.

Sector demands

We include seven key sectors in our scenarios (Fig. 1): residential-commercial electricity, residential-commercial heating, land transport, aviation, shipping, industry (including industrial feedstock) and energy demand in agriculture. In the base scenario, technological transformations that modify final energy demands in every sector are included (e.g. electric vehicles increase electricity demand in road transport and reduce diesel demand), but energy services demands are assumed to remain at today’s level (e.g. passenger-kilometres). In the following section, we will describe changes in energy services demand that we investigate in this study, and provide examples of those for different sectors (e.g. passenger-kilometres reduction due to home-office). Demands for different energy carriers in the base scenario for every sector are

shown in Fig. 1. Detailed methodologies for constructing demand in every sector taking into account technological transformations have been covered in previous studies²⁴, and we only summarize the most relevant information here.

Residential and commercial electricity demand, which we refer to as electricity sector, is represented using hourly demand profiles for each country, derived from 2013 ENTSO-E data²⁷. These profiles account for electricity use in cooking, cooling, and rail transport amongst others. To allow endogenous optimization of capacities providing heat, current electrified heating is removed from these profiles. In the base scenario, no exogenous electricity demand growth or reduction is assumed relative to current levels. However, total electricity demand increases endogenously due to e.g. the electrification of heating and the complete transition of land transport to electric vehicles. The primary sources of flexibility in the electricity sector include pumped hydro storage (fixed at today’s capacities), as well as endogenously optimized batteries at high-voltage and low-voltage levels, electrolyzers along with hydrogen stores, and synthetic production of methane, methanol and oil.

Heating demand encompasses residential and commercial requirements for space heating and hot water, which we refer to as heating sector. Daily profiles for space heating are based on heating degree days and hourly consumption patterns that vary by sector (residential or service), and account for weekdays, weekends, and holidays^{28,29}. These profiles are scaled to match each country’s annual heating demand in 2013, which is an average year²¹. Spatial distribution of heat demand within countries is weighted by population density, distinguishing between urban and rural areas. 60% of urban heat demand is assumed to be supplied through district heating systems^{15,16}. Thermal energy storage is modeled as small water tanks that allow buffering for a few hours in individual systems and central large water tanks that enable seasonal balancing in district heating systems¹¹. For the base scenario, we assume space heating demand at today’s level, which makes our base results more expensive than other similar net-zero analyses in PyPSA-Eur that by default assume a 29% space heating reduction due to buildings retrofitting²⁴.

Land transport demand is assumed to be fully electrified. Country-level electricity demand for electric vehicles (EVs) is calculated using a fixed EV efficiency of 0.18 kWh/km and the current country-specific energy consumption of internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles. Therefore, more efficient EVs effectively reduce overall energy demand in this sector in 2050. Hourly electricity demand from EVs is modeled using country-specific driving profiles from the BAST database³⁰, adjusted for local time and incorporating additional heating or cooling loads based on ambient temperature. Only 50% of idle vehicles allow smart charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G). Each EV battery is modeled with an average storage capacity of 50 kWh, a charging capacity of 11 kW, and 90% efficiency for both charging and discharging. EV batteries are requested to be at least 75% charged by 7 a.m., preventing their use for seasonal storage. The EV fleet and associated infrastructure incur no investment costs in the model, as we assume consumers purchase cars for personal use.

Aviation demand includes both domestic and international flights, and is supplied by kerosene which can have fossil origin or be synthetically produced via Fischer-Tropsch process. Shipping is assumed to operate entirely on methanol. For both aviation and shipping, annual demands need to be supplied, but the model can decide when to produce the synthetic fuels throughout the year.

Energy demands in agriculture including electricity, heat, and oil are calculated per country using JRC-IDEES²⁸ and Eurostat²⁹ databases, with electricity and heat demands assumed to be constant throughout the year. Similar to aviation, oil for agriculture is an annual demand and can be produced based on endogenous model decision.

The industry sector includes energy and feedstock demands from major European industries such as iron and steel production, chemicals, non-metallic minerals, pulp and paper, and non-ferrous metals. Industrial demands are spatially distributed based on the locations of existing industrial facilities from the Hotmaps Industrial Database³¹. While materials production volumes are assumed to remain unchanged from current levels²⁸, we implement sector-specific transformations, described in detail by Neumann et al.²⁴ and summarized here.

Integrated steelworks is fully phased out and substituted by assuming that the recycling route covers 70% of steel demand and the rest is obtained via direct reduced iron (DRI). Similarly, aluminium recycling is assumed to increase so that it represents 80% of total demand. Mechanical and chemical recycling of plastics is assumed to cover 30% and 20% of total plastic demand. Complete electrification is assumed for low-temperature heat as well as many industrial processes that allow it. Biomass is assumed for medium-temperature heat, while methane and hydrogen are assumed for high-temperature heat. Although certain transformations, such as the share of DRI in steel production, are fixed exogenously, the model incorporates multiple processes to enable endogenous decisions for feedstock production. For instance, hydrogen can be generated via electrolysis or steam methane reforming (SMR) with or without carbon capture. Methane can be produced through the Sabatier process, biogas upgrading, or imported as liquefied natural gas (LNG) from outside Europe. Industrial demands for electricity, low-temperature heat, and hydrogen are assumed to be constant throughout the year. Demands for gas, naphtha, solid biomass, and methanol are imposed annually, and the model can decide when to produce them.

In summary, the model incorporates a range of flexibility mechanisms across sectors to account for temporal and spatial balancing of energy supply and demand. Time-shifting flexibility is provided by storage options for electricity (batteries, PHS, and EV batteries), hydrogen, heat (water tanks), gas, and CO₂ (temporary in overground tanks and permanently when sequestered underground). Additionally, methanol, oil, biogas, and solid biomass can be stored at no cost since only annual balances are imposed. Spatial flexibility is enabled through exchange of electricity (AC and DC transmission lines) and methane (pipelines). Methanol, oil, and solid biomass can also be transported at no cost and without limit in the model.

Modeling of alterations in energy service demands

We analyse four stylised representations of service-demand reduction or shifting (Fig. 6). Each of the four demand-side mechanisms is applied independently for different sectors. For example, we apply constant demand reduction separately for each of the seven sectors by 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40%, while keeping the demand at the reference level in the remaining sectors. This leads to 35 sensitivity scenarios for this mechanism, and we compare a total of 124 scenarios to the base to evaluate the system-wide benefits in terms of total costs, emissions, and capacities. We apply service demand alterations at the sector level rather than by energy carrier. For example, reducing demand in the electricity sector (comprising residential and buildings) does not affect electricity use in agriculture or industry, as these are changed under their respective sectors (see Fig. 1a and definitions of the electricity and heating sectors in the previous section). The four service-demand alteration mechanisms are summarized below.

(i) Constant service-demand reduction: A uniform reduction in demand by a fixed percentage is applied throughout the year (Fig. 6a). Examples of behavioural changes that can be represented by this mechanism include increased use of public transport, cycling, car-sharing, or home-office that reduce passenger-kilometres travelled by EVs, using smaller vehicles or driving them at reduced speeds, setting lower indoor-temperature targets for heating systems, using electrical appliances with higher efficiency in residential or industrial applications, and implementing circular-economy strategies or more conscious consumers that reduce demand for products, and consequently demands in the industry and shipping sectors.

(ii) Peak shaving: Under this mechanism, any demand exceeding a certain percentage of the peak demand (defined as the difference between the maximum and minimum demand) is curtailed (Fig. 6b). This simulates consumers' behaviour changes during peak demand periods, such as lowering their consumption because they react to very high electricity prices published by the market operator in day-ahead markets. In reality, peak shaving is difficult to achieve, and the curtailed demand will most likely shift to a later or earlier period⁸. A more realistic approach would involve incentives for private and industrial consumers to reduce their consumption, as described below for the demand curtailment mechanism.

(iii) Demand time shifting: This mechanism introduces a cost-free ideal storage at every node, representing consumer behaviour that shifts energy consumption (Fig. 6c). This free storage is located at the same bus as the sector demand, which is the low-voltage (LV) bus for electricity and urban and rural heat buses for heating (see Supplementary Note 1). The storage is lossless, unlike the standing loss assumed for hot water storage or the round-trip efficiency of batteries, and there is no limit on the power capacity for discharging or charging it. We vary the energy capacity of the storage, which we refer to as the storage size, from 0.01% to 0.1% of annual demand. Example of this mechanism in the real world are initiatives such as dynamic electricity pricing or time-of-use grid tariffs, which are designed to shift consumers' demand to off-peak periods.

(iv) Demand curtailment: Instead of considering inelastic demand, this mechanism allows demand

Fig. 6: **Stylised representation of the four demand alteration mechanisms.** (a) Constant reduction (b) Peak shaving (c) Demand time shifting (d) Demand curtailment.

curtailment, also known as load shedding, when the price reaches a certain threshold (Fig. 6d). This represents a stylised one-step utility function, i.e., consumers are only willing to consume if the price remains below their utility (threshold). More advanced representations of demand flexibility available in PyPSA¹⁸ are not included here. Examples of these mechanisms are interruptibility services in Spain, where large industrial consumers, such as aluminium smelters, are paid to be ready to shut off when requested by the transmission system operator (TSO), or demand response programs in the U.S., where both private and industrial consumers are financially incentivized to reduce consumption during specific hours³².

Mechanisms (i) and (ii) are implemented exogenously, meaning demand profiles are altered before optimization. In contrast, mechanisms (iii) and (iv) allow the model to determine, endogenously, when and where to activate demand shifting or demand curtailment in a cost-optimal way.

Here, we focus on the system-level impacts of different demand reduction schemes. Potential trade-offs between reductions in system costs and reduced consumer utility or external investment costs to achieve our demand alteration mechanisms are beyond the scope of this study. Therefore, except for demand curtailment, we assume all mechanisms are achieved at no cost and do not account for potential rebound effects, such as increased passenger-kilometres traveled due to more efficient vehicles.

Limitations

In this paragraph, we briefly mention the main limitations of our approach. All our mechanisms to represent alterations in energy service demands are simplified. In particular, we represent demand elasticity with a one-step function and neglect other, more elaborate, representations¹⁸. We model demand curtailment for residential and services electricity demand, heating demand and EVs demand, but do not model demand elasticity in industry. We do not assess implementation costs of each demand reduction scenario due to

uncertainties^{33, 35}, limiting a complete cost-benefit analysis. We also ignore potential sectoral shifts, e.g., remote work lowering transport demand but raising residential electricity and heating demand.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve readability. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Author contributions

P.R. and M.V. jointly conceptualised the study, designed the methodology, contributed to the modeling, and carried out the investigation. P.R. drafted the original manuscript, analysed the data, and created visualisations. M.V., M.S., and A.C.L. contributed substantial reviews of the manuscript. M.V. supervised the investigation.

Data and code availability

The model is implemented using the open energy modeling framework PyPSA and makes use of the model PyPSA-Eur v0.11.0³⁶(available under MIT license via github.com/PyPSA/pypsa-eur/) and the costs and technology assumptions included in the technology-data v0.9.0²⁵(github.com/PyPSA/technology-data). Scripts to reproduce the results and figures included in this paper are publicly available at: github.com/Parisra/Demand-management-paper

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Supplementary Note 1. PyPSA-Eur model

PyPSA-Eur models the European energy system by utilizing comprehensive datasets to create demand profiles for sectors including electricity, heating, industry, aviation, shipping, and agriculture. The model also incorporates weather data, renewable energy cost assumptions, land availability for renewable installations, industrial site locations, and the geographical distribution of salt caverns for hydrogen storage (see more details regarding the optimization constraints, data sources, and technology assumptions in Neumann et al.^[24] as well as the model documentation^[36]).

The model encompasses 33 European countries, which include all EU27 members (except Malta and Cyprus), as well as Albania, Great Britain, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, and Switzerland. The spatial resolution is adjustable, allowing each country to be represented by either a single node or multiple nodes. Spatial aggregation is performed using k-means clustering. Temporal resolution in PyPSA-Eur can range from a single hour to a year. Temporal aggregation is carried out using segmentation clustering via the tsam package^[37]. This approach ensures that variations in supply and demand are preserved by clustering only adjacent snapshots based on their time-series similarity.

The main objective function for the optimization is to minimise the total annualized system costs by optimizing capacity and dispatch of different technologies for one year, as shown in Eq. (S1)

$$\min_{G,F,E,P,g,f} = \left[\sum_{i,r} c_{i,r} \cdot G_{i,r} + \sum_k c_k \cdot F_k + \sum_{i,s} c_{i,s} \cdot E_{i,s} + \sum_l c_l \cdot P_l + \sum_{i,r,t} w_t \left(\sum_{i,r} o_{i,r} \cdot g_{i,r,t} + \sum_k o_k \cdot f_{k,t} \right) \right] \quad (\text{S1})$$

where c_* is capital cost of the component, o_* is operating cost of the component, $G_{i,r}$ is generator capacity of technology r at location i , $E_{i,s}$ is energy capacity of storage s at location i , P_l is transmission line capacity for line l , F_k is power capacity of technology k for conversion and transportation of energy, $g_{i,r,t}$ is generator dispatch of technology r at time t , and $f_{k,t}$ is dispatch of technology k , for instance storage dispatch, or dispatch of transmission lines and gas-to-biogas converters, at time t . Each time snapshot t is weighted by the time-step w_t , and the sum of time-steps is one year. Costs for all technologies and the source for each data are available at the GitHub repository of PyPSA Technology Data^[25].

Various constraints to the optimisation represent different physical and societal limitations in the real-world energy system. For example, demand is usually considered inelastic and must be met at each time-step. A carbon emissions limit is set for a scenario if we want to understand the transition needed to reach climate targets. For each renewable technology, e.g. wind and solar, a maximum renewable potential is calculated in every region based on land availability, and available renewable generation throughout the year is estimated based on weather data. PyPSA-Eur allows customisation of many variables within the model using additional linear constraints, e.g. limiting maximum transmission expansion to reflect social acceptance, or the share of electric vehicles available for use as storage.

For each region or node, separate buses that represent different energy carriers are interconnected by links that simulate energy conversions, such as electrolysis (electricity to hydrogen) or fuel

cells (hydrogen to electricity). Buses representing the same energy carrier can be connected to each other if they represent a real-world energy transportation method, such as transmission lines between electricity buses. To reduce computational demands, some carriers (e.g., kerosene) are often "copper-plated" and represented with a single European bus, assuming seamless access without transmission costs or losses, which also means ignoring any possible bottlenecks. Figure S1 shows a simplified representation of how the electricity, heating, and land-transport sector are connected to each other in our model. Figure S2 shows how the gas bus and the hydrogen bus in each node are connected to electricity and heat generators, storage technologies, pipelines to other nodes, separate demands such as gas for industry, and finally to each other in the form of chemical processes.

Fig. S1: Simplified representation of a single node when modeling the electricity, heating, and land-transport sector. This figure has been designed using images made by Iconjam (utility battery, heat pump), NeXore88 (Fuel Cell), and freepik (all other icons) from flaticon.com.

Fig. S2: Simplified representation of the gas and hydrogen bus of a single node when modeling all the sectors. For detailed information on different processes within the system refer to Neumann et al. [24](#). The land transport bus is where battery electric vehicles (BEV), their chargers (BEV charger), and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) are connected. This figure has been designed using images made by NeXore88 (Fuel Cell) and freepik (all other icons) from flaticon.com.

In this study, we include two demand reduction scenarios that represent demand shifting and demand curtailment, the latter involving compensation for private and industrial consumers to

reduce their consumption. To model demand shifting, an ideal lossless storage without any charging/discharging constraint is added to the model. For demand curtailment (also called load shedding), a generator with zero capital investment and high marginal cost is added to the model. Both the free storage and the load shedding generator are located at the same bus as the sector demand. For electricity, this is the low-voltage bus. For heating, the free storage and the load shedding generator are added to the urban and rural heat buses, which are connected to the low-voltage bus with technologies such as heat pumps and resistive heaters. For land-transport, demand is located at a separate bus connected to the low-voltage bus at each node, as shown in Fig. S3

Fig. S3: Representation of how the Land-transport is modeled in PyPSA-Eur, and how different demand reduction scenarios are implemented. The electric vehicle battery (BEV) is modeled as a store with energy capacity of 50 kWh. BEV charging and V2G are modeled as links with 90% efficiency. Land-transport demand has a daily profile specific to each European country. This figure has been designed using an image made by freepik from flaticon.com

Supplementary figures

Figure S4: Base scenario composition for (a) total system costs, (b) installed technology capacities, and (c) energy balance. Energy balance shows a summary of all energy generation and energy demands considered in the model. The system relies primarily on solar PV (utility-scale, rooftop, and horizontal-tracking) and wind (onshore and offshore), which contribute 29% and 35% of total generation, respectively. Heat pumps are the next largest energy contributors, followed by biomass, which is used for both electricity generation (CHPs) and heat production in the residential (boilers) and industrial sectors. .

Figure S5: Reduction of: (a) total system costs and (b) CO₂ price for constant demand reduction in different sectors, normalised to the annual demand of each sector. Aviation and shipping yield the greatest benefits per unit of final energy reduced, making demand reduction in these sectors more effective than in others. However, because their overall demand is relatively low, the absolute savings are smaller (see Fig. 2 in the main text). These two sectors depend on high-cost production of synthetic oil (through Fischer-Tropsch units) and methanol, both of which require captured carbon.

Figure S6: Variation of: (a,b,c) total system costs and (d,e,f) CO₂ price for all four demand alteration mechanisms, compared for electricity, heating, and land transport. The x-axis of each plot represents equivalent annual demand alteration scenarios. For example, shaving electricity peaks by 50% reduces annual demand by about 10% (see inset of Fig. 2 in main text), so this scenario is represented by 10% demand alteration.

Figure S7: Variation of: (a,c,e,g) total system costs and (b,d,f,h) CO₂ price, normalised to the annual demand of each sector, for all four demand alteration mechanisms, compared for electricity, heating, and land transport. The x-axis of each plot represents equivalent annual demand alteration scenarios. For example, shaving electricity peaks by 50% reduces annual demand by about 10% (see inset of Fig. 2d in main text), so this scenario is represented by 10% demand alteration.

Fig. S8: Relative changes in power capacity of different technologies for (a) 40% constant demand reduction, (b) 50% peak shaving, (c) free storage with size equal to 0.1 % of annual sector demand, and (d) load shedding with cost of 200 €/MWh. Some technologies such as hydropower, run of river, and pumped hydro storage, are cost-efficient for all scenarios even under high demand reduction and their capacity remains unchanged.

Fig. S9: Absolute changes in technology costs for (a) 40% constant demand reduction, (b) 50% peak shaving, (c) free storage with size equal to 0.1 % of annual sector demand, and (d) load shedding with cost of 200 €/MWh.

Fig. S10: Relative changes in energy capacity of storage technologies for (a) 40% constant demand reduction, (b) 50% peak shaving, (c) free storage with size equal to 0.1 % of annual sector demand, and (d) load shedding with cost of 200 €/MWh.

Fig. S11: Relative changes in fossil oil and gas imports to Europe (TWh/a) for (a) 40% constant demand reduction, (b) 50% peak shaving, (c) free storage with size equal to 0.1 % of annual sector demand, and (d) load shedding with cost of 200 €/MWh.

Fig. S12: (a) Share of annual demand reduction to peak shaving for electricity, heating, and land-transport. The rest of the figures show duration curves for (b) electricity demand, (c) heating demand, and (d) land-transport demand, and how 40/50/60% peak shaving would crop the demand curve. Peak shaving is relative to peak demand, which is defined as the difference between the maximum and minimum demand.

Fig. S13: Changes in the rolling daily mean of (a) electricity demand and (b) heating demand when a free storage with size equal to 0.1% of annual demand for each sector is available. The shifted demand is calculated by adding the net power being discharged from the free storage (negative when charging happens) to the demand.

Fig. S14: Average weekly profile of heating demand and shifted heating demand when a free storage with total size equal to 0.1% of heating demand is available at rural and urban heat buses for (a) Spain in summer, (b) Spain in winter, (c) Denmark in winter, and (d) Denmark in summer.

Fig. S15: Nodal distribution of (a) average marginal price of electricity and (b) standard deviation of the marginal price of electricity for the base scenario.

Fig. S16: Nodal distribution of (a) average marginal price of heating and (b) standard deviation of the marginal price of heating for the base scenario.

Fig. S17: Changes in the annual mean of shadow price of electricity and heating for (a) constant demand reduction, (b) peak shaving, (c) demand shifting with free storage, and (d) load shedding. The green stars (see Fig. 2 of main text) represent scenarios altering roughly 5% of annual demand. Average nodal marginal price of electricity and heating for the base scenario can be seen in Supplementary Figs. S15 S16.

Fig. S18: Country-wise changes in shadow price of heating, which can be thought of as what consumers pay for heating, for (a) 5% annual demand reduction , (c) 40% peak shaving, (e) free storage size equal to 0.04% of annual heating demand, and (g) heat shedding with price of 200 €/MWh. Figures (b), (d), (f), and (h) show the changes in standard deviation of heating price, which can be thought of as price volatility, for the mentioned scenarios, respectively. The selected scenarios are almost equivalent in terms of annual heating demand that is altered (see green star scenarios in Supplementary Fig. [S17](#)).

Fig. S19: Changes in total system cost for each country (sum of capital costs and marginal costs, excluding pipelines and transmission lines) under scenarios that are roughly equivalent in terms of annual electricity demand being altered (see green star scenarios in Fig. 2 of main text): (a) 5% annual demand reduction , (b) 40% peak shaving, (c) free storage size equal to 0.02% of annual demand, and (d) load shedding with price of 250 €/MWh. Note that while total system cost decrease for all scenarios, system costs for individual countries can increase

Fig. S20: Share of each technology in country-wise system cost changes under different demand mechanisms for the electricity sector: (a) 40% annual demand reduction, (b) 50% peak shaving, (c) free storage size equal to 0.1% of annual demand, and (d) load shedding with price of 200 €/MWh. For example, when down-scaling electricity demand by 40% in (a), total system cost for North Macedonia is reduced by 25%, and almost half of this cost reduction is achieved by reducing the cost of battery in the country. Total system cost for each country is the sum of capital costs and marginal costs, excluding pipelines and transmission lines. Countries are ordered by the net reduction in total system cost, meaning the left-most country in each figure has the highest system cost reduction, while the right-most country has the lowest reduction or the highest increase.

Fig. S21: CO₂ balances in the system for the base and 40% constant demand reduction scenario of different sectors. The left bar for each scenario shows the CO₂ balance for the atmosphere, i.e. the carbon emitted into the atmosphere (marked *(1)) by technologies such as gas turbines, and the carbon captured (marked *(3)) by technologies such as direct air capture (DAC). The right bar shows the CO₂ balance for the amount of CO₂ stored, with technologies such as biomass CHP with carbon capture storing the CO₂ (marked *(2)), and technologies such as methanolisation utilizing the stored CO₂ (marked *(4)). All scenarios have a maximum carbon sequestration limit of 200 Mega-tonnes/a. The emission intensity of the system (total emitted CO₂ from column *(1) divided by total system demand) rises for electricity-40% (4%), heating-40% (9%), industry-40% (2%), and land-transport-40% (2%); and decreases for aviation-40% (-6%), shipping-40% (-10%), and agriculture-40% (-1%).

Fig. S22: CO₂ capture in the system for the base and scenarios with significant DAC reduction. The bar for each scenario shows the different ways CO₂ is captured from the atmosphere (See Supplementary Fig. S21 for more information).